

International Journal of Network Security & Its Applications (IJNSA)

(UGC Listed, ERA Listed)

ISSN 0974 - 9330 (Online); 0975 - 2307 (Print)

<http://airccse.org/journal/ijnsa.html>

Current Issue: May 2019, Volume 11, Number 3

Enhancing the Wordpress System: from Role to Attribute-Based Access Control

Lifeng Cao, Jia Ying Ou and Amirhossein Chinaei, York University, Canada

Classification Procedures for Intrusion Detection Based on KDD CUP 99 Data Set

Shaker El-Sappagh, Ahmed Saad Mohammed and Tarek Ahmed AlSheshtawy, Benha University, Egypt

Xdoser, A Benchmarking Tool for System Load Measurement Using Denial of Service Features

AKM Bahalul Haque, Rabeya Sultana, Mohammad Sajid Fahad , MD Nasif Latif and Md. Amdadul Bari, North South University, Bangladesh

Multi-Layer Classifier for Minimizing False Intrusion

Shaker El-Sappagh, Ahmed saad Mohammed and Tarek Ahmed AlSheshtawy, Benha University, Egypt

Methods Toward Enhancing RSA Algorithm : A Survey

Shaheen Saad Al-Kaabi and Samir Brahim Belhaouari, Hamad Bin Khalifa University (HBKU), Qatar

Survey on Secure Routing in Vanets

Afef Slama¹ and Ilhem Lengliz², ¹University of Manouba, Tunisia and ²Military Academy, Tunisia

A Combination of Temporal Sequence Learning and Data Description for Anomaly - based NIDS

Nguyen Thanh Van^{1,2}, Tran Ngoc Thinh¹ and Le Thanh Sach¹, ¹Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology, VietNam and ²Ho Chi Minh City University of Technology and Education, VietNam

http://airccse.org/journal/jnsa19_current.html